

Nature-Based Protection Strategies for Environmental Protection Areas in Çanakkale

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Abstract

Çanakkale, located at the intersection of the Aegean and Marmara regions, represents a unique geographical and ecological transition zone in Türkiye. Hosting diverse ecosystems from the 5 location the region embodies the complex interplay between nature, culture, and history. This study aims to develop and evaluate nature-based protection strategies to enhance the sustainability and resilience of Çanakkale's environmental protection areas. Through an integrated geographical approach, the research identifies ecological pressures such as unplanned urbanization, tourism intensity, mining activities, and agricultural expansion that threaten the integrity of these protected zones. Using geographical based spatial analysis, field observations, and ecological assessment methods, the study explores adaptive management frameworks that prioritize ecosystem services, biodiversity conservation, and cultural landscape preservation. The findings suggest that integrating geography-based stewardship with ecosystem-based planning could significantly strengthen local resilience while fostering a balance between conservation and socio-economic needs.

Keywords: Environment, protected areas, Çanakkale

Çanakkale'de Çevre Koruma Alanlarına Doğa Temelli Koruma Stratejileri

Öz

Ege ve Marmara bölgelerinin kesiştiği noktada bulunan Çanakkale, Türkiye'de eşsiz bir coğrafi ve ekolojik geçiş bölgesi temsil etmektedir. Bölge, 5 farklı ekosisteme ev sahipliği yaparak doğa, kültür ve tarih arasındaki karmaşık etkileşimi somutlaştırmaktadır. Bu çalışma, Çanakkale'nin çevre koruma alanlarının sürdürülebilirliğini ve dayanıklılığını artırmak için doğaya dayalı koruma stratejileri geliştirmek ve değerlendirmek amacıyla yapılmıştır. Entegre bir coğrafi yaklaşımla, araştırma, bu koruma alanlarının bütünlüğünü tehdit eden plansız kentleşme, turizm yoğunluğu, madencilik faaliyetleri ve tarımsal genişleme gibi ekolojik baskıları belirlemektedir. Coğrafi temelli mekansal analiz, saha gözlemleri ve ekolojik değerlendirme yöntemlerini kullanarak, çalışma ekosistem hizmetlerini, biyolojik çeşitliliğin korunmasını ve kültürel peyzajın korunmasını önceliklendiren uyarlanabilir yönetim çerçevelerini incelemektedir. Bulgular, coğrafi temelli yönetim ile ekosistem temelli planlamanın entegre edilmesinin, koruma ve sosyoekonomik ihtiyaçlar arasında bir denge sağlarken yerel direncin önemli ölçüde güçlendirilebileceğini göstermektedir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Çevre, koruma alanları, Çanakkale.

1. Introduction

Protected areas have become increasingly strategic worldwide in terms of sustaining ecosystem services, conserving biodiversity, and building climate resilient landscapes (Watson et al., 2014; Mace et al., 2012; Gül & Metin, 2021). These areas not only ensure the sustainability of natural life but also support the preservation of water resources, the maintenance of carbon sinks, the safeguarding of cultural heritage, and the promotion of nature based education (Chape et al., 2005; CBD, 2020). The concept of the national park was institutionalized with the establishment of Yellowstone National Park in the United States in 1872 and was later adopted by many other countries (Runte, 1997). Today, parks such as Banff in Canada, Maasai Mara in Kenya, Kakadu in Australia, and Berchtesgaden in Germany serve as exemplary models for conservation, environmental education, and sustainable tourism (Phillips, 2003; Eagles et al., 2002). Among the protected area categories defined by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), national parks (Category II) are among the most effective tools for biodiversity conservation (Dudley, 2008). However, areas equivalent to Special Environmental Protection Zones (SEPZs) in many countries are defined under different names; in Europe as the “Natura 2000” network, in the United States as “Critical Habitat Zones,” in Australia as “Environment Protection Zones,” and in the Mediterranean Basin as “Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)” all established to achieve sustainable environmental management (Agardy et al., 2003; Ban et al., 2011; European Environment Agency, 2021).

Globally, game reserves are areas designed for the sustainable management of wildlife populations, based on principles of controlled hunting and ecological planning. These areas are not solely intended for sport hunting but are also evaluated in terms of conservation, monitoring, and local development goals (Boitani et al., 2008). In South Africa, privately managed “game reserves” hold strategic importance for both biodiversity conservation and local community participation in the economy (Child, 2009). The “community based conservancy” model implemented in Namibia serves as a successful example where hunting tourism directly contributes to village economies (Naidoo et al., 2011). In countries such as the United States and Canada, game management is carried out through scientifically grounded “Wildlife Management Units” (WMUs), where hunting quotas are determined according to biocapacity (Organ et al., 2012).

1.1. Definition and Purpose

The conservation and sustainable use of natural resources constitute one of the most critical elements of contemporary environmental governance. In this context, Türkiye’s *Specially Protected Environmental Areas (SPEAs)* and *National Parks* represent two major legal frameworks established to ensure ecosystem protection and the sustainable management of biodiversity. Despite sharing overarching objectives, these two protection categories differ significantly in their definitions, management approaches, and implementation frameworks.

SPEAs are designated areas established according to specific criteria to protect ecosystems and natural or cultural values. These regions often focus on safeguarding coastal and marine ecosystems exposed to intensive human pressure. The management of SPEAs involves the development of targeted strategies for the conservation of particular ecosystems or natural resources (Erdal & Aydoğdu, 2016).

National Parks, on the other hand, are extensive areas designated to preserve natural beauty, biological diversity, and ecosystem integrity. In addition to conservation goals, they aim to support tourism, recreation, and socio-economic activities, contributing to both environmental and local community welfare (T.C. Çevre, Şehircilik ve İklim Değişikliği Bakanlığı (ÇŞİDB), 2022). As Dudley (2008) emphasizes, the purpose of National Parks extends beyond preservation it also encompasses the enhancement of local livelihoods.

1.2. Legal Framework

The management of SPEAs in Türkiye is regulated under Decree Law No. 383, issued in 1988. This legislation provides a legal framework for the protection of ecosystems and natural resources within specifically designated zones (Erdal & Aydoğdu, 2016). National Parks, however, are governed by the *National Parks Law No. 2873*, which outlines the procedures for their establishment, conservation, and

management. The primary legal basis for National Parks emphasizes the preservation of both natural and cultural heritage (Gül & Metin, 2021; Küçük & Ertürk, 2013).

1.3. Protected Area Scope and Coverage

SPEAs are generally smaller, ecologically sensitive areas that focus on protecting specific habitats or ecosystems, such as coastal and marine ecosystems, wetlands, and habitats for rare or endemic species. Management strategies in these areas are tailored to address localized environmental threats (Atik et al., 2012). National Parks, by contrast, encompass broader and more diverse landscapes. They are designed to conserve natural resources while simultaneously promoting ecotourism and recreational activities. These areas aim to preserve natural beauty and the rich diversity of flora and fauna (Eagles et al., 2002).

1.4. Authorization and Management

Human activities such as construction, agriculture, and other land use practices are strictly controlled within SPEAs. Permissions are typically granted by centralized authorities, and participatory governance mechanisms remain limited. This top down management approach can restrict local community involvement in decision making processes (Erdal & Aydoğdu, 2016). National Parks, conversely, provide more opportunities for local participation. Activities such as tourism, hiking, and camping may be permitted under regulated conditions. Nonetheless, these activities must comply with strict ecological limits to prevent environmental degradation (Dudley, 2008).

1.5. Conservation Strategies

Conservation strategies in SPEAs primarily emphasize ecosystem restoration and rehabilitation. Targeted interventions are implemented to mitigate environmental degradation and manage ecological risks (Atik et al., 2012). National Parks adopt broader conservation approaches that balance nature protection with the promotion of ecotourism and sustainable use of natural resources (Eagles et al., 2002). Both protection types contribute significantly to maintaining biodiversity and ecosystem services. However, their goals and management approaches differ substantially. SPEAs are predominantly focused on protecting vulnerable coastal and marine ecosystems through stricter regulatory mechanisms, whereas National Parks promote flexible, community oriented management models that integrate conservation with tourism and local development.

Specially Protected Environmental Areas and National Parks represent two complementary yet distinct conservation models in Türkiye's environmental management framework. While both play crucial roles in protecting natural and cultural assets, they differ in their legal foundations, management structures, and strategic objectives. SPEAs prioritize stringent protection against environmental threats and anthropogenic pressures, whereas National Parks emphasize inclusive governance and sustainable tourism development. These differences are central to shaping the country's broader conservation strategy. Ultimately, ensuring the sustainable management of Türkiye's natural heritage requires the effective implementation of both protection categories, the resolution of existing management challenges, and the continuous alignment of conservation objectives with socio-ecological realities.

Türkiye, with its high biodiversity, diverse climatic zones, and multi-layered cultural landscape, functions as an ecological bridge between Europe and the Middle East (Myers et al., 2000). In this context, nature conservation policies have gained momentum in the country since the 1980s. The first Special Environmental Protection Zone (SEPZ) was established in Köyceğiz-Dalyan in 1988, leading to the formation of the Special Environmental Protection Agency (Özel Çevre Koruma Kurumu ÖÇKK, 2009). In 2011, this institution was integrated into the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change. As of 2023, there are 19 SEPZs across Türkiye (ÇŞİDB, 2023). National parks, on the other hand, are protected under Law No. 2873 on National Parks and are managed by the General Directorate of Nature Conservation and National Parks (DKMP). As of 2022, 45 national parks have been designated in Türkiye, managed in a planned manner to ensure both natural landscape conservation and the development of nature-based tourism (DKMP, 2023). For example, Kazdağları National Park is recognized as one of the centers of biodiversity due to its endemic flora, while the Historical National Park of Troy represents a unique integration of archaeological and natural heritage

and has been recognized by UNESCO (Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı, 2018; UNESCO, 2019). In conclusion, national parks, SEPZs, and hunting areas in Türkiye are not only intended for nature conservation but also function as integrated spaces that serve environmental education, ecotourism, local development, and cultural heritage protection. Their educational potential is particularly valuable for advancing nature-based learning approaches within the context of geography education (Rickinson et al., 2004; UNESCO, 2021).

2. Material and Method

This research aims to analyze the administrative, ecological, and educational functions of Special Environmental Protection Zones (SEPZs), national parks, and game reserves in Türkiye. It adopts a qualitative research framework based on the analysis of multiple data sources. The study integrates document analysis, comparative evaluation, SWOT analysis, and spatial analysis methods (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2021; Creswell, 2013).

3. Findings and Discussion

Within this framework, the present study examines Special Environmental Protection Zones (SEPZs), national parks, and historical conservation areas in Türkiye from an ecological and spatial management perspective. Concentrating on emblematic examples within the Çanakkale Province namely the *Marmara Sea and Islands SEPZ*, the *Saros Gulf SEPZ*, *Kazdağı (Mount Ida) National Park*, the *Troy Historical National Park*, and the *Gallipoli Historical Area of the Çanakkale Wars* the research explores how these zones collectively function as ecological corridors and landscape mosaics that sustain biodiversity and ecosystem services across terrestrial, coastal, and marine environments. These protected areas represent distinct yet interconnected ecosystems where biotic and abiotic processes, such as hydrological dynamics, soil vegetation interactions, and habitat connectivity, illustrate the complexity of regional ecological networks and also The “21st century environmental literacy” skills emphasized by UNESCO can be effectively fostered through such field based educational practices (UNESCO, 2021; Rickinson et al., 2004). From a conservation standpoint, the study emphasizes the interdependence between natural and cultural landscapes, highlighting how anthropogenic pressures such as tourism, urban expansion, and agricultural intensification pose challenges to ecological resilience. At the same time, these areas serve as critical reference sites for monitoring climate change impacts, species migration, and habitat degradation patterns within the northwestern Anatolian context. Thus, the integrated assessment of these landscapes contributes to a deeper understanding of ecosystem integrity, adaptive management strategies, and the sustainability of Türkiye’s protected area system.

3.1. Saros Gulf Special Environmental Protection Area

The Saros Gulf SEPA (Special Environmental Protection Area) extends across both Edirne and Çanakkale provinces (Total Area: Approximately 105,000 hectares (including both terrestrial and marine zones). Within Çanakkale, the area particularly encompasses the northern and northwestern coasts of the Gallipoli Peninsula. The protected boundaries include lands belonging to two towns (Kavakköy and Evreşe) and twelve villages (Bolayır, Değirmendüzü, Demirtepe, Fındıklı, Güneyli, Karainebeyli, Kocaçeşme, Koruköy, Ocaklı, Şadılı, Tayfur, and Yeniköy) within the Gallipoli District of Çanakkale Province, as well as Beşyol village in the Eceabat District of Çanakkale and Yeniköy settlement in the Şarköy District of Tekirdağ Province. The residential areas of five villages (Bolayır, Güneyli, Koruköy, Ocaklı, and Yeniköy) fall directly within the SEPA boundaries. The region also contains two islands under protection.

Fauna:

- Fish Species: Economically significant species such as *Dentex dentex* (common dentex), *Sparus aurata* (gilthead seabream), and *Dicentrarchus labrax* (European seabass) use the area as spawning and nursery grounds.
- Marine Mammals: Occasional sightings of *Delphinus delphis* (common dolphin) and *Tursiops truncatus* (bottlenose dolphin) have been reported within the gulf.

- Marine Turtles: The Saros Gulf occasionally serves as a transit route for *Caretta caretta* (loggerhead sea turtle).
- Waterbirds and Migratory Species: Lagoon systems provide crucial breeding and resting habitats for ducks and herons.

Flora:

- Seagrasses: *Posidonia oceanica* and *Zostera noltei* form the foundation of the coastal marine ecosystem.
- Coastal Dune Plants: Salt tolerant and sand binding species such as *Elymus farctus*, *Cakile maritima*, and *Ammophila arenaria* stabilize the coastal dunes.
- Lagoon Vegetation: *Phragmites australis* (common reed) and *Typha* species are widespread along lagoon and freshwater margins.

Rationale for Protection:

The gulf is characterized by low pollution levels relative to the Mediterranean, a natural self cleaning circulation system (notably a “reverse current”), and highly sensitive ecosystems including seagrass meadows (*Posidonia oceanica*). It also hosts rich fish biodiversity and holds significant potential for diving tourism. The SEPA designation aims to protect both terrestrial and marine habitats as a unified ecological system (Figure 1, Table 1).

Figure 1. Location of the Saros Bay Conservation Area

Table 1. SWOT Analysis: The Gulf of Saros (Saros Körfezi)

Strengths	Weaknesses
- One of the most pristine marine ecosystems in the northern Aegean Sea, with high water clarity and strong self-cleaning capacity due to hydrodynamic circulation	- Limited institutional coordination between coastal municipalities and marine protection authorities
- Rich biodiversity including endemic and migratory fish, seagrass meadows (<i>Posidonia oceanica</i>), and marine mammals	- Insufficient monitoring and enforcement against illegal fishing and coastal pollution
- Recognized as a Specially Protected Area (SPA) under national legislation	- Inadequate infrastructure for wastewater treatment in surrounding settlements
- Potential for sustainable diving, ecotourism, and marine education activities	- Limited local awareness and stakeholder participation in conservation initiatives
- Important spawning and nursery area for commercial fish species	- Seasonal tourism pressure leading to habitat degradation and litter accumulation

Opportunities	Threats
- Development of eco-tourism and blue economy initiatives supporting local livelihoods	- Increasing risk of marine pollution from maritime transport and oil/gas exploration
- Strengthening cooperation with universities for marine research and conservation	- Overfishing and habitat destruction caused by trawling and unregulated fishing
- Potential inclusion in international conservation frameworks (e.g., RAMSAR or UNESCO Marine Biosphere Reserve)	- Climate change effects such as rising sea temperature and invasive species proliferation
- Educational and citizen-science programs for sustainable marine awareness	- Urbanization, coastal construction, and loss of natural dunes and wetlands

3.2. Marmara Sea and Islands Special Environmental Protection Area

This SEPA encompasses coastal areas bordering the Marmara Sea across multiple provinces. Within Çanakkale, the Gallipoli and Eceabat districts' Marmara facing coastal zones are included. Specifically, the Kumkent area (195 hectares) and the Kumkale Delta (108 hectares) are under protection. Despite being under intense industrial and residential pressure, the Marmara Sea still retains valuable coastal and marine ecosystems that warrant protection. Along the Çanakkale coastline, this protection is crucial for marine birds, shallow water ecosystems, benthic habitats, and coastal fisheries. The SEPA designation seeks to regulate coastal development and mitigate marine pollution in these vulnerable ecosystems.

Fauna:

- Marine Species: *Mugil cephalus* (flathead mullet), *Engraulis encrasicolus* (European anchovy), and *Gobius* species represent small benthic fish communities.
- Seabirds: The region lies on a major migratory route, hosting *Larus* spp. (gulls), *Sterna* spp. (terns), and *Puffinus yelkouan* (Yelkouan shearwater).
- Benthic Organisms: *Holothuria* spp. (sea cucumber), *Octopus vulgaris* (common octopus), and various mollusks enrich the benthic biodiversity.

Flora:

- Marine Vegetation: Algal communities such as *Cystoseira* spp. and seagrass meadows of *Posidonia oceanica* play a critical role in oxygen production and carbon sequestration.
- Coastal Vegetation: Coastal areas are covered by Mediterranean shrubs and grass species adapted to saline environments.

General Evaluation

The province of Çanakkale holds a strategic position within Türkiye's coastal protection policies due to its long coastline, island ecosystems, and the presence of three distinct seas namely the Aegean, the Marmara, and the transitional zone toward the Black Sea through the Saros Gulf along the Edirne border. The existence of Specially Protected Environmental Areas (SPEAs) encompassing Gökçeada, the Saros Gulf, and the Marmara Sea highlights Çanakkale's significance both for the conservation of biological diversity and for the development of nature based tourism.

However, despite their protection status, coastal pressures such as tourism driven construction, the exceeding of carrying capacities, marine pollution, and coastal privatization continue to pose significant threats in these regions. Therefore, the SPEA designation should not remain a mere legal framework; it must be reinforced through effective planning, monitoring, and participatory management involving local communities.

Çanakkale's multi layered natural heritage can achieve a sustainable balance between conservation and tourism only if guided by the principles of Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM). With its diverse coastal typologies, marine ecosystems, and cultural landscapes, the province stands as one of

the most strategic regions within Türkiye’s coastal protection agenda. The northwestern extensions of the Saros Gulf SPEA, along with the coastal sections of the Marmara Sea and Islands SPEA that encompass Gelibolu and Eceabat, constitute the principal areas ensuring the protection of Çanakkale’s natural assets. These areas host a wide range of biological components such as seagrass meadows, endemic plant species, benthic habitats, marine mammals, and migratory birds while also interacting with fisheries and tourism activities under the principles of sustainable use. Nevertheless, these ecosystems remain vulnerable due to increasing coastal pressures, unplanned development, the exceeding of ecological carrying capacities, and climate change–induced environmental stress.

In this context, the sustainability of conservation objectives within Çanakkale’s SPEAs depends on the integration of active ecosystem management, science based monitoring programs, and local community participation, rather than relying solely on legal boundary definitions (Figure 2, Table 2).

Figure 2. Location of the Marmara Sea and Islands Special Environmental Protection Area

Table 2. SWOT Analysis: Specially Protected Environmental Areas (SPEAs) in Türkiye

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legal protection of 19 ecologically sensitive areas across Türkiye - Habitat provision for key species (e.g., Mediterranean monk seal) - Strong legal basis aligned with national and international conventions (e.g., Decree-Law, Bern Convention, Ramsar) - Suitable natural settings for ecotourism and environmentally friendly activities - Opportunities for sustainable tourism that can support local economies - Rich biodiversity and active environmental education initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Frequent institutional restructuring and administrative uncertainties - Challenges in the practical implementation of management plans - Insufficient monitoring, infrastructure, and financial resources - Limited participation of local communities in management processes - Tourism-related construction pressures threatening environmental integrity
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential support through EU harmonization processes and international environmental funds - Promotion of participatory and decentralized governance models - Development of ecotourism and nature-based economic models - Integration of digital monitoring and conservation technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Over-tourism, unplanned development, and coastal degradation - Impacts of climate change on water resources and ecosystems - Conflicts with local communities and mismatched economic expectations - Inadequate protection measures and increasing illegal activities

Türkiye has designated 19 Specially Protected Environmental Areas (SPEAs) as a key component of its biodiversity conservation strategy. These areas play a crucial role in maintaining ecological integrity and promoting sustainable resource use. The current assessment of SPEAs reveals a complex interplay of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, emphasizing the need for stronger institutional coordination, adaptive management, and science policy integration to ensure long-term ecological sustainability.

3.3. Kazdağı (Mount Ida) National Park

The ancient name of Kazdağı is *Mount Ida*. It is one of Türkiye's and the world's most ecologically significant regions, hosting numerous endemic plant species. In terms of oxygen concentration, Kazdağı ranks second in the world after the Alps (Öztura, 2010). Geographically, the mountain is located between 39°30'–39°52' N latitude and 26°30'–27°14' E longitude (Özel, 1999), while another study specifies the coordinates of Kazdağı National Park as 26°44'03"–26°59'59" E and 39°34'09"–39°44'34" N (Poyraz, 2013). By the decree of the Council of Ministers (Decision No. 93/4243) published in the Official Gazette No. 21555 on April 17, 1994, a 21,300 hectare section within the boundaries of Edremit District (Balıkesir Province) was designated as *Kazdağı National Park* (Figure 3, Table 3).

Figure 3. Location of the Kazdağı (Mount Ida) National Park

Table 3. SWOT Analysis: Kaz Dağları National Park:

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exceptional biodiversity with more than 800 plant taxa, including endemic species such as <i>Abies equi-trojani</i> - High oxygen concentration and pristine natural environment suitable for ecotourism - Legally protected status since 1994 under national conservation law - Important ecological corridor in the North Aegean biogeographical region - Potential for environmental education and scientific research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing mining and infrastructure pressures in surrounding buffer zones - Limited capacity for visitor management and insufficient sustainable tourism strategies - Weak enforcement of protection laws and fragmented institutional responsibilities - Local community involvement and awareness on conservation issues remain limited - Conflicts between conservation goals and economic interests (e.g., tourism, agriculture)
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of eco-friendly tourism and educational trails 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uncontrolled tourism and illegal forest clearing activities

Opportunities	Threats
- International cooperation through biosphere reserve or UNESCO recognition	- Climate change impacts threatening endemic flora and fauna
- Enhancement of local livelihoods through sustainable forestry and agriculture	- Industrial pollution and mining exploration near the park boundaries
- Promotion of Kaz Dağları as a model for biodiversity-based conservation	- Deforestation and water resource depletion due to regional population growth

Natural Richness of Kazdağı National Park represents one of the most biologically diverse areas in Türkiye (Gül et al., 2006). Scientific research has identified approximately 800 plant taxa within the park, though the actual number is estimated to approach 1,000. Among them, the *Kazdağı fir (Abies equi-trojani)*, which grows exclusively in this region, stands out as a highly valuable endemic species. In addition to its floristic diversity, the park also sustains rich fauna, including mammals such as bears, roe deer, wild boar, foxes, jackals, wildcats, and lynx, as well as various bird and reptile species. This ecological diversity results from the coexistence of multiple habitat types, ranging from alpine meadows and coniferous forests to river valleys and mixed woodlands.

3.4. Troy Historical National Park

The *Troy Historical National Park* is located in northwestern Türkiye, within the boundaries of the Ezine District of Çanakkale Province. The area was declared a national park on September 30, 1996, by decision of the Council of Ministers and covers approximately 13,350 hectares. The park is notable for its combination of archaeological, historical, and natural values. Situated near the village of Tefikiye, at the intersection of the Aegean Sea and the Dardanelles Strait, the park's landscape is characterized by low ridges, alluvial valleys, and flat plains. The principal rivers of the region Karamenderes and Dümrek have played a vital role in the formation of the Kumkale Delta, contributing significantly to the local ecosystem.

Archaeological and Cultural Significance of The most prominent archaeological site within the park is the *Ancient City of Troy*, famously described in Homer's *Iliad*. The site has been continuously inhabited since 3000 BCE and bears traces of several successive civilizations. In 1998, Troy was inscribed on the *UNESCO World Heritage List*.

Beyond the ancient city itself, the park contains five tumuli, five ancient settlements, three monumental structures, two registered cemeteries, four artillery positions, and one war memorial associated with the Gallipoli Campaign. In 2018, to commemorate the 20th anniversary of Troy's inclusion on the UNESCO World Heritage List, the *Troy Museum* was inaugurated, housing archaeological findings from Troy and its surrounding region.

Natural Richness of apart from its archaeological importance, Troy Historical National Park also features remarkable natural diversity. Botanical surveys have identified approximately 312 plant and tree species, seven of which are endemic. Common species include *Pistacia terebinthus* (terebinth), *Arbutus unedo* (strawberry tree), *Quercus coccifera* (kermes oak), *Vitex agnus-castus* (chaste tree), and *Corylus colurna* (Turkish hazel).

The park's fauna includes wild boar, foxes, jackals, martens, and numerous bird species. Particularly, the Kumkale Delta serves as a critical stopover site for migratory birds, enhancing the ecological value of the park within regional biodiversity networks (Figure 4, Table 4).

Figure 4. Location of the Troy Historical National Park

Table 4. SWOT Analysis: Troy Historical National Park:

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unique combination of cultural and natural heritage, including the UNESCO-listed Troy Ancient City - Contains multiple archaeological layers representing millennia of human settlement - Rich biodiversity with over 300 plant species, including 7 endemic taxa - Strong symbolic value in world cultural heritage and literature - Existence of the modern Troy Museum supporting public awareness and research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited integration between archaeological conservation and landscape management - Insufficient infrastructure for visitor management and interpretive services - Dependence on seasonal tourism economy - Limited coordination between local authorities and heritage institutions - Erosion and agricultural pressures affecting archaeological integrity
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of cultural routes linking Troy with other heritage sites - Integration of sustainable tourism with local products and crafts - Strengthening community-based heritage interpretation programs - International recognition increasing funding and conservation partnerships 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Urban expansion and agricultural encroachment into protected areas - Climate variability and flooding risks in low-lying deltaic zones - Visitor overcapacity and infrastructure pressure during peak seasons - Potential neglect of natural habitats due to focus on archaeology

3.5. Gallipoli Historical Area of the Çanakkale Wars

The *Gallipoli Historical Area of the Çanakkale Wars* is located in the Marmara Region within the province of Çanakkale and stands as one of the most symbolically significant cultural landscapes in Türkiye. The *Gallipoli Campaign* of 1915, fought between the Ottoman Empire and the Allied Powers during World War I, unfolded on this peninsula. Beyond its military importance, the site has become a space of transnational collective memory and reconciliation. Originally declared as the *Gallipoli Peninsula Historical National Park* in 1973, the area was redefined as the *Çanakkale Wars Gallipoli Historical Area* following the enactment of Law No. 6546 on June 28, 2014. With this reclassification, it transitioned from a national park to a historical area status.

Covering approximately 33,444 hectares, the area hosts 50 Turkish war cemeteries, 29 Turkish monuments and inscriptions, 34 foreign memorials and cemeteries, 49 monumental structures, 138 examples of traditional civil architecture, and several 15th century Ottoman military buildings. The landscape also contains shipwrecks, artillery, trench lines, and fortifications, offering tangible evidence of the war's material heritage.

Natural and Cultural Landscape of The Gallipoli Peninsula constitutes not only a historical battlefield but also a distinctive natural environment. The region's natural assets include coves, beaches, Mediterranean maquis vegetation, forest remnants, and geomorphological formations such as the Suvla Salt Lake. These features contribute to the area's ecological and visual diversity, forming a unique synthesis of cultural memory and natural beauty.

Today, the Gallipoli Historical Area is among the most visited war heritage sites in Türkiye and one of the few well preserved battlefields in the world. It serves as a crossroad of *history, culture, nature, and international remembrance*, embodying a shared commitment to peace and collective heritage (Figure 5, Table 5).

Figure 5. Location of the Gallipoli Historical Area (Çanakkale Wars Historical Site)

Table 5. SWOT Analysis: Gallipoli Historical Area (Çanakkale Wars Historical Site):

Strengths	Weaknesses
- Exceptional historical and memorial value with 50 Turkish cemeteries and 34 foreign memorials	- Management complexity due to multi-national heritage sensitivity
- One of the best-preserved World War I battlefields worldwide	- Limited integration between cultural heritage preservation and environmental protection
- Strong legal protection under Law No. 6546 and dedicated management authority	- Seasonal tourism leading to overuse of specific sites
- Combined natural and cultural landscapes enhancing visitor experience	- Insufficient transportation and interpretation infrastructure in peripheral zones
- High symbolic importance for peace and reconciliation tourism	- Erosion and natural degradation of trenches, monuments, and coastal areas

Opportunities	Threats
- Promotion of memory-based and peace-oriented international tourism	- Environmental degradation caused by mass tourism and waste accumulation
- Establishment of integrated cultural landscape management models	- Sea-level rise and coastal erosion affecting heritage structures
- Development of educational and digital heritage platforms	- Political sensitivities and conflicting narratives about war history
- Collaboration with UNESCO and ICOMOS for heritage conservation	- Potential loss of authenticity due to over-commercialization

4. Conclusion and Suggestions

The integrated ecological and cultural landscapes of northwestern Türkiye particularly those within the Çanakkale region embody a delicate balance between natural systems and historical heritage. The Marmara Sea and Islands Special Environmental Protection Area (SEPZ), Saros Gulf SEPZ, Kazdağı (Mount Ida) National Park, Troy Historical National Park, and the Gallipoli Historical Area of the Çanakkale Wars collectively represent a unique mosaic of biodiversity, geomorphological diversity, and millennia old human history. These protected areas not only safeguard endemic flora and fauna but also preserve the tangible and intangible cultural legacies that define the region's identity.

However, this coexistence of nature and culture is increasingly threatened by human induced pressures. Expanding agricultural activities, uncontrolled tourism development, transportation infrastructure, wildfires, and urban encroachment have led to habitat fragmentation, loss of biodiversity, and degradation of archaeological and cultural landscapes. In particular, the intensification of coastal tourism and the expansion of road networks around sensitive ecosystems such as the Saros Gulf and Marmara Islands have accelerated ecological stress and disrupted traditional land use patterns. Similarly, in Kazdağı National Park, recurrent forest fires and agricultural clearing threaten endemic plant species and the park's microclimatic stability, while the Troy and Gallipoli areas face cumulative impacts from mass visitation and inadequate site management. These pressures illustrate the urgent need for integrated ecosystem management that reconciles conservation objectives with sustainable human use. Strengthening the ecological connectivity between terrestrial and marine zones, enforcing carrying capacity limits in tourism planning, and enhancing fire and pollution monitoring systems are critical components of such an approach. Furthermore, fostering community participation and cultural landscape conservation can transform local populations from passive beneficiaries into active stewards of their natural heritage.

In conclusion, the Çanakkale region serves as a microcosm of the broader environmental challenges faced by heritage landscapes across the Mediterranean. Preserving the intertwined legacy of nature and history requires an adaptive and interdisciplinary conservation framework one that addresses the root causes of environmental degradation while sustaining the ecological, cultural, and symbolic values that define this region's global significance. Only through such holistic stewardship can the continuity of both ecological integrity and cultural memory be ensured for future generations.

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The article complies with national and international research and publication ethics. No ethics committee approval was required for this study.

Author Contribution and Conflict of Interest Disclosure Information

As the sole author of the article, he has contributed fully. There is no conflict of interest.

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